

TO'RINCHI TARTIBLI INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN TO'G'RI
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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda to'rtinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglama uchun bir teskari masala bayon qilingan va tadqiq etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: to'rtinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglama, Riman-Liuvill ma'nosida γ (kasr) tartibli integral, chegaraviy shartli, teskari masala.

ПРЯМАЯ И ОБРАТНАЯ ЗАДАЧА ДЛЯ ИНТЕГРО-ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНОГО
УРАВНЕНИЯ ЧЕТВЕРТОГО ПОРЯДКА

Аннотация: В этой работе была сформулирована и исследована обратная задача для Интегро-дифференциального уравнения четвертого порядка.

Ключевые слова: Интегро-дифференциальное уравнение четвертого порядка, Интеграл Римана-Лювилля в смысле (дроби), граничное условие, обратная задача.

A DIRECT AND INVERSE PROBLEM FOR AN INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL
EQUATION OF THE FOURTH ORDER

Annotation: In this paper, the inverse problem for a fourth-order Integro-differential equation was formulated and investigated.

Keywords: Integro-differential equation of the fourth order, Riemann-Liouville integral in the sense of (fractions), boundary condition, inverse problem.

So'ngi vaqtlarda noma'lum manbali differensial tenglamalar bilan shug'illanishga bo'lgan qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Bunga sabab ko'plab issiqlik taqalish va diffuziya jarayonlarini matematik modelini tuzish noma'lum manbali differensial tenglama uchun qo'yiladigan masalalarga keltiriladi. Bunday differensial tenglamalar uchun teskari masalalar ko'plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o'rganilgan (masalan, ushbu [1]–[7] ishlarga qaralsin). Ammo yuqori tartibli tenglamalar uchun teskari masalalar kam o'rganilgan. Shu sababdan biz ushbu ishda to'rtinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglama uchun bir teskari masalani bir qiymatli yechilishini ko'rsatamiz.

(0, 1) oraliqda ushbu

$$y^{(4)}(x) - \lambda I_{0,x}^{\gamma} y(x) = f(x) \quad (1)$$

to`rtinchi tartibli integro-differensial tenglamani qaraylik, bu yerda $y(x)$ – noma'lum funksiya; $f(x)$ – berilgan uzluksiz funksiya; λ, γ - o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar bo'lib; $I_{0x}^\gamma y(x)$ - Riman-Liuuill ma'nosida γ (kasr) tartibli integral,

$$I_{0x}^\gamma y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\gamma-1} y(t) dt,$$

A masala. Shunday $y(x)$ funksiya topilsinki, u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo'lsin:

1) $(0, 1)$ oraliqda (1) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;

2) $C^3[0,1] \cap C^3(0,4)$ sinfga tegishli bo'lsin;

3) $x=0, x=1$ nuqtalarda esa

$$y(0) = A_1, y'(0) = A_2, y(1) = B_1, y'(1) = B_2 \quad (2)$$

chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 – berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar.

(1) tenglamani

$$y(0) = A_1, y'(0) = A_2, y''(0) = A_3, y'''(0) = A_4 \quad (3)$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini

$$y(x) = A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_3 x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_4 x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) + \int_0^x (x-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz$$

ko'rinishda yozib olishimiz mumkin [7], bu yerda A_3 va A_4 no'malum sonlar, B_1 va B_2 berilgan o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar.

A_3, A_4 ni $y(1) = B_1, y'(1) = B_2$ chegaraviy shartdan foydalanib,

$$A_3 = - \frac{A_1 [E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)] + A_2 [E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)]}{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)} - \frac{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)} + \frac{B_1 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - B_2 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)}$$

$$A_4 = - \frac{A_1 [E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)] + A_2 [E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)]}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} - \frac{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} + \frac{B_1 E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - B_2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)}$$

ko'rinishda topamiz.

Topilgan A_3, A_4 ni (3) ga qo'yib, (1) masala yechimini

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(x) = & x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{A_1 [E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)] + A_2 [E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)]}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] - \\
 & - x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{A_1 [E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)] + A_2 [E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)]}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + \\
 & + B_1 \left[\frac{-x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) + x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,1}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + \\
 & + B_2 \left[\frac{x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) - x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + \int_0^x (x-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz + \\
 & + \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \left[\frac{x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + \\
 & + \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \left[\frac{-x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) + x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

ko‘rinishda topamiz.

1-teorema. Agar $E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \neq 0$, $f(x) \in C[0,1]$ bo‘lsa u holda A masala yagona yechimga ega bo‘ladi va u (4) formula bilan aniqlanadi.

1-izoh. Agar $E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) = E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)$ bo‘lsa, u holda A masala yechimga ega bo‘lmaydi.

$$y^{(4)}(x) - \lambda I_{0x}^\alpha y(x) = kf(x) \quad (5)$$

T masala. Shunday $y(x)$ funksiya va k son topilsinki, u quyidagi xossalarga ega bo‘lsin:

1) $(0, 1)$ oraliqda (5) tenglamani qanoatlantirsin;

2) $C^3[0,1] \cap C^3(0,4)$ sinfga tegishli bo‘lsin;

3) $x=0$, $x=1$ nuqtalarda esa (2) chegraviy shartni va

$$y''(1) = b \quad (6)$$

nolokal shartni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2, b - o'zgarmas haqiqiy sonlar bo‘lib.

k sonmi vaqtincha ma‘lum deb, T masalaning yechimini (4) formuladan foydalanib,

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(x) = & -kx^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] - \\
 & - x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{A_1 \{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)\} + A_2 \{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)\}}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{B_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - B_2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] - x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{B_1 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - B_2 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + \\
 & +kx^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + \\
 & +x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) \left[\frac{A_1 \{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)\} + A_2 \{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)\}}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \right] + \\
 & +A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + k \int_0^x (x-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

ko‘rinishda yozib olamiz.

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= \frac{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \\
 M_1 &= \frac{A_1 \{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)\} + A_2 \{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)\}}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \\
 M_2 &= \frac{B_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - B_2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}, \quad N_2 = \frac{B_1 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - B_2 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \\
 N_1 &= \frac{A_1 \{E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)\} + A_2 \{E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) E_{\beta,4}(\lambda)\}}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)} \\
 N &= \frac{E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz - E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) \int_0^1 (1-z)^2 E_{\beta,3}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz}{E_{\beta,4}(\lambda) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - E_{\beta,3}(\lambda) E_{\beta,3}(\lambda)}
 \end{aligned}$$

belgilashlarni kiritib, $y''(x)$ ni

$$\begin{aligned}
 y''(x) &= -Mkx E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) - (M_1 - M_2)x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) + kN E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + (N_1 - N_2) E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + \\
 & + A_1 \lambda x^{\beta-2} E_{\beta,\beta-1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 \lambda x^{\beta-1} E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda x^\beta) + k \int_0^x (x-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz
 \end{aligned}$$

ko‘rinishda aniqlaymiz. Topilgan $y''(x)$ ni (6) shartga bo‘ysuntirib, k ni

$$k = \frac{b + (M_1 - M_2) E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - (N_1 - N_2) E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - A_1 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta-1}(\lambda) + A_2 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda)}{\left(-M + N + \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \right)} \tag{8}$$

ko‘rinishda topamiz.

(8) formulani (7) formulaga qo‘yib, $y(x)$ funksiyani

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(x) = & -Mx^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) \frac{b + (M_1 - M_2)E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - (N_1 - N_2)E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - A_1 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta-1}(\lambda) + A_2 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda)}{\left(-M + N + \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz\right)} + \\
 & + Nx^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) \frac{b + (M_1 - M_2)E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - (N_1 - N_2)E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - A_1 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta-1}(\lambda) + A_2 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda)}{\left(-M + N + \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz\right)} + \\
 & + \int_0^x (x-z)^3 E_{\beta,4}[\lambda(x-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \frac{b + (M_1 - M_2)E_{\beta,2}(\lambda) - (N_1 - N_2)E_{\beta,1}(\lambda) - A_1 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta-1}(\lambda) + A_2 \lambda E_{\beta,\beta}(\lambda)}{\left(-M + N + \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz\right)} - \\
 & - (M_1 - M_2)x^3 E_{\beta,4}(\lambda x^\beta) + (N_1 - N_2)x^2 E_{\beta,3}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_1 E_{\beta,1}(\lambda x^\beta) + A_2 x E_{\beta,2}(\lambda x^\beta) \quad (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

ko‘rinishda aniqlaymiz.

2-teorema. Agar $-M + N + \int_0^1 (1-z) E_{\beta,2}[\lambda(1-z)^\beta] f(z) dz \neq 0, f(x) \in C(0,1)$ bo‘lsa u

holda T masala yagona yechimga ega bo‘ladi va u (8) va (9) formulalar bilan aniqlanadi.

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